

● Creating Data Management Plans with NFDI4Ing RDMO*

2023-10-27 NFDI4Ing Community Meeting CC-42

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Base Service S1

rdmo@nfdi4ing.de

* RDMO = Research Data Management Organiser

Research Data Management

Why?

- Traceability and transparency of scientific results
- Validation and verifiability of scientific results
- Reproducibility of scientific results
- Improve data quality

- **Reusable data**

Baker, Monya (2016): 1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility. In Nature 533 (7604), pp. 452–454. <https://doi.org/10.1038/533452a>.

Research Data Management

Funder requirements

- DFG Code of Conduct guideline 7 (quality assurance), guideline 13 (public access), guideline 17 (archiving)
- Checklist
de: <https://www.dfg.de/forschungsdaten/checkliste>
en: https://www.dfg.de/research_data/checklist
- **RDM part of good research practice**

Information for Researchers No. 25 | 14 March 2022

Specification of Requirements Relating to the Handling of Research Data in Funding Proposals

It will now be mandatory for proposals to include details

One essential component of quality-oriented, compatible research is that the data a research project is based on or generates is handled in a way that is appropriate to the subject-specific discipline. The Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) has now specified its requirements for the handling of research data in proposals for individual and collaborative projects and has made it mandatory to include details.

The digital turn in science and the humanities has stimulated access to research data, methodological developments in the processing of research data and analytical methods of answering complex research questions through data management. In almost all disciplines, there is a growing awareness that the handling of research data used or generated in projects is an essential requirement for the verifiability and compatibility of research: as a result, this aspect has now become established as an essential component of academic quality. Adequate handling of research data requires sound project planning and integration of specific competences and structures.

Research Data Management

FAIR

- Findable
- Accessible
- Interoperable
- Reusable

Data management plan

What is a DMP?

- Part of project management and quality assurance
- structures the handling of research data in a research project
- describes how to deal with data used during and after project completion
- is expected by third-party funding agencies as part of a funding proposal

Data management plan

DMP Templates

- e.g.
 - DFG checklist
 - Horizon Europe Template
 - RDMO catalogs
- guiding the planning process
- supporting the communication on data management in a project team

Checklist Regarding the Handling of Research Data

1. Data description
How does your project generate new data? Is existing data reused? Which data types (in terms of data formats like image data, text data or measurement data) arise in your project and in what way are they further processed? To what extent do these arise or what is the anticipated data volume?
2. Documentation and data quality
What approaches are being taken to describe the data in a comprehensible manner (such as the use of available metadata, documentation standards or ontologies)? What measures are being adopted to ensure high data quality? Are quality controls in place and if so, how do they operate? Which digital methods and tools (e.g. software) are required to use the data?
3. Storage and technical archiving the project
How is the data to be stored and archived throughout the project duration? What is in place to secure sensitive data throughout the project duration (access and usage rights)?
4. Legal obligations and conditions
What are the legal specifics associated with the handling of research data in your project? Do you anticipate any implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility? What is in place to consider aspects of use and copyright law as well as ownership issues? Are there any significant research codes or professional standards to be taken into account?
5. Data exchange and long-term data accessibility
Which data sets are especially suitable for use in other contexts? Which criteria are used to select research data to make it available for subsequent use by others? Are you planning to archive your data in a suitable infrastructure? If so, how and where? Are there any retention periods? When is the research data available for use by third parties?
6. Responsibilities and resources
Who is responsible for adequate handling of the research data (description of roles and responsibilities within the project)? Which resources (costs; time or other) are required to implement adequate handling of research data within the project? Who is responsible for curating the data once the project has ended?

Motivation

A service to support the planning process

RDMO supports you in

- Complying with funder requirements
- Planning data management
- Identifying open issues

- rdmo.nfdi4ing.de

rdmo.nfdi4ing.de

[Feedback](#) [Language](#) ▾

Welcome to RDMO

The tool enables researchers of engineering to create a data management plan (DMP) for their research project. After logging in with and one time activation of your DFN account you can choose from several templates that guide you through the different aspects of a DMP.

[Login](#)

[SIGN IN with ORCID !\[\]\(f95dab70c751fda7d824b8b03650f7aa_img.jpg\)](#)

We appreciate your feedback

rdmo@nfdi4ing.de

Maintenance window

Tuesday 6:30 am - 8:30 am

Our service

rdmo.nfdi4ing.de

One central RDMO service

- Login via NFDI-AAI
- DMP template for researchers of engineering sciences

RDMO clients for all NFDI4Ing participants

Multitenant RDMO instance allows for customizing

- Theme
- Login (e.g. via Shibboleth)
- URL
- DMP templates

NFDI4Ing Template

Create a new project

 Feedback Language ▾ Jürgen Windeck ▾

Create new project

Title
The title for this project.

Description
A description for this project (optional).

Catalog
The catalog which will be used for this project.

NFDI4Ing_template
Catalog according to the DFG checklist of December 21, 2021

Parent project
The parent project of this project.

NFDI4Ing Template

Project overview

NFDI4ing Feedback Language ▾ Jürgen Windeck ▾

My new project

Description	A short description of the project.	Options
Catalog	NFDI4Ing_template Catalog according to the DFG checklist of December 21, 2021	Answer questions View answers

Tasks

Tasks are generated automatically from the answers given in the project. On the page of each task you can see which of your answers lead to the activation of the task.

No active tasks found.

Views

Views are created using the answers given in the project and can then be exported in various formats. Initially, all views are empty. Please answer some questions by visiting **Answer Questions** (at the top of the sidebar).

No views are configured for this project.

Members

Here you can see who can access the project and invite additional members. You can use the user roles to manage which rights the benefits have. Unless you are the last owner, you can leave the project with the button next to your name.

User	E-Mail	Role	+
Jürgen Windeck	juergen.windeck@tu-darmstadt.de	Owner	

Snapshots

Export

- RDMO XML
- CSV comma separated
- CSV semicolon separated

Import values

Import from file

NFDi4ing Template

Invite members

 [Back to project](#)

Invite member to project

You can invite a new member to this project and assign one of the following roles: **Guest** (who can only read), **Author** (who can answer questions), **Manager** (who can additionally create snapshots, export the project, import values, and update the project settings) or **Owner** (like you).

Users can be invited by their username (if they already have an account here), or by their e-mail address.

Users will receive an e-mail with a link to join the project with the assigned role.

User

The username or e-mail of the new user.

Role

Owner

Manager

Author

Guest

NFDI4Ing Template

NFDI4Ing template

- For researchers of engineering sciences
- based on RDA survey and workshops in NFDI4Ing
- follows dfg checklist:
https://www.dfg.de/research_data/checklist
- First version – feedback welcome!

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Content data description" with the NFDI4ing logo in the top left. The form includes a breadcrumb "NFDI4ing Vorlage Test → Data description" and a link "Data description". The main text explains that the catalog is a checklist published by the DFG, intended to help structure data management. It asks users to define a logical unit of research data as a data set. A "Read more..." link is provided. Below this, instructions state that users should fill in the form for each set and can add, edit, or delete sets. The form has a "Set" button and an "Add set" button. A section titled "What kind of dataset is it?" contains a list of checkboxes for various data types: tables, Binary or numeric data, code, simulation data, algorithm, Measurement data e.g. from test benches, image data, Big Data (heterological data types), references, textual data, visual recordings, and Other: (with an input field).

NFDI4ing

NFDI4ing Vorlage Test → Data description

Content data description

The present catalog is the checklist published by the DFG supplemented by engineering content. The DFG checklist must be submitted with the application and at the end of the project and is intended to help you structure your data management. If you have any questions, please get in touch with the responsible contact person.

The following questions are intended to describe the datasets that are created and/or used in the project. The definition of what a data set is is an important conceptual decision that must be made individually for each undertaking or project. Choose a logical unit of your research data as the data set, for which the same information regarding methodology, technology, accessibility, etc. applies.

[Read more...](#)

Please fill in the form for each set. The different sets will be referred to in following questions. You can add a new set using the green button. Once created, you can edit or delete sets using the buttons in the top right corner.

Set [Add set](#)

What kind of dataset is it?

- tables
- Binary or numeric data
- code
- simulation data
- algorithm
- Measurement data e.g. from test benches
- image data
- Big Data (heterological data types)
- references
- textual data
- visual recordings
- Other:

NFDI4ing Template

Add datasets

—● e.g. one set for each type of data

The screenshot shows the 'Content data description' page in the NFDI4ing system. The page title is 'Content data description' and it includes a breadcrumb trail: 'My Projects / My research project / Data description'. The main content area contains several paragraphs of instructions and a green 'Add set' button. A red arrow points from this button to a modal window titled 'Set'. The modal has a 'Title' field containing the text 'Simulation' and a note: 'Please give the set a meaningful name.' At the bottom of the modal are 'Close' and 'Save' buttons. On the right side of the page, there is a sidebar with sections: 'Overview' (Project: My research project, Catalog: NFDI4ing_template), 'Progress' (9 of 25), and 'Navigation' (Using the navigation will save your input. Entries with © might be skipped based on your input. A list of navigation items is visible: data description, Content data description, Technical data description, Documentation and data quality, Storage and technical backup during th..., Legal obligations and framework condit..., Data exchange and permanent accessib..., Responsibilities and resources).

NFDI4Ing Template

Your data

 Feedback Language ▾ Jürgen Windeck ▾

Will existing data be reused?

Existing data is often reused in engineering. They can form the basis of the new project or only be used for parts of the project. When using existing data, also think about data you use to compare your data.

The sources of the reused data range from working group internal databases, e.g. for DFT calculations, to open and freely accessible databases such as Kaggle, to (openly accessible) repositories such as Zenodo or, more specifically, the Sequence Read Archive (SRA). Very often data from databases like *Open Quantum Materials*, *Inorganic Crystal Structure Database*, *Materials Project*, *AtomWorkAdv.* or *MAGNDATA* reused.

- simulation data
- measurement data e.g. from test benches
- experimental, microbial and/or genomic data
- sequenced data such as parts of a production plan used to form a production order
- Material properties and other material data from databases or from tables in various journals
- Source code from GitHub or the following open source software:
- 3D models
- Calculations for Heusler alloys and MAB components
- weather data
- Open Street Map data
- Output and model parameters for standardized models such as FEM
- open data from public databases such as Kaggle
- data from social media
- Reuse of data generated by your own working group or associated groups in previous projects
- No, no existing data will be used.

Overview

Project: [NFDI4Ing Vorlage Test](#)
Catalog: [NFDI4Ing_template](#)
[Back to my projects](#)

Progress

BackSkip

Navigation

Please note that using the navigation will discard any unsaved input.

Entries with @ might be skipped based on your input.

[Data description](#)
→ [Content data description](#)
 [Technical data description](#)

[Documentation and data quality](#)
[Storage and technical backup during th...](#)
[Legal obligations and framework condit...](#)
[Data exchange and permanent accessib...](#)
[Responsibilities and resources](#)

NFDI4Ing Template

Topics

- Documentation
- Quality measures
- Storage and backup
- Data exchange
- Legal obligations, responsibilities and resources

 [Back to project](#)

[My Projects](#) / [My research project](#) / [Documentation and data quality](#)

Dokumentation

Which approaches are followed in order to describe the data in a comprehensible manner (e.g. use of existing metadata or documentation standards or ontologies)?

Metadata standards are used for the structured documentation of data. Here, both general standards such as ISO or Dublin Core as well as engineering-specific standards such as Metagenomics Sequences Sample (MIMS), International Data Spaces Information Model or ACM Computing Classification are used.

If you are not using a metadata standard, please provide individual metadata for this question. These can be e.g. the device or simulation settings, the test parameters and the workflow. The software (incl. version) and the hardware also count here. Administrative metadata is also often documented, such as the date, name of the responsible scientist, the project, etc.

- The following standards, classifications, etc. are used:
- A proprietary description system is used, which looks like this:
- The following metadata are used to describe the data:
- The following metadata is used to describe the environmental conditions (e.g. machine, employee):
- Other:
- The documentation, including the metadata specified above, is provided via a ReadMe file.
- The documentation, including the metadata specified above, uses the following naming convention:
- The documentation, including the metadata specified above, takes place via the following electronic laboratory journal:
- It has not yet been decided which system will be used to describe the metadata and context information.

What digital methods and tools (e.g. software) are required to use the data?

In order to be able to reuse data, in addition to the data itself, the software, devices, etc. and knowledge of special procedures for use are required. Since use can vary greatly depending on the sub-area in engineering, please exchange ideas with your colleagues.

NFDI4Ing Template

NFDI4Ing template

NFDI4ing

Feedback Sprache ▼ Jürgen Windeck ▼

Antworten für *NFDI4Ing Vorlage Test*

Im Folgenden haben wir die von Ihnen eingegebenen Informationen über das Projekt noch einmal zusammengefasst.

Datennutzung

Inhaltliche Datenbeschreibung

Um was für einen Datensatz handelt es sich?

Set *"experimental data"*:

- Tabellen
- Code
- Bilddaten

Auf welche Weise entstehen in Ihrem Projekt neue Daten?

Set *"experimental data"*: Laborversuche

Werden existierende Daten wiederverwendet?

Set *"experimental data"*: Simulationsdaten

Technische Datenbeschreibung

Welche Datentypen, im Sinne von Datenformaten entstehen in Ihrem Projekt?

Set *"experimental data"*:

- (text) *.pdf
- (text) *.tex
- (text) *.odt
- (data) *.gnu
- (data) *.m

Auf welche Weise werden die Daten in Ihrem Projekt weiterverarbeitet?

Optionen

[Zurück zum Projekt](#)

Export

- PDF
- Rich Text Format
- Open Office
- Microsoft Office
- HTML
- Markdown
- mediawiki
- LaTeX

What's new?

Feedback Language -

Welcome to RDMO

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We appreciate your feedback

rdmo@nfdi4ing.de

Maintenance window

Tuesday 6:30 am - 8:30 am

Login

SIGN IN with ORCID

Software Management Plan (SMP)

Create new project

Title
The title for this project.

Description
A description for this project (optional).

Catalog
The catalog which will be used for this project.

NFDI4ing_template
Catalog according to the DFG checklist

Software Management Plan
This catalogue is for the management of scientific software projects. It supports scientists in the development organisation of software developments through fifty questions in different topic blocks. This catalogue is available in the [Planck Digital Library](#)

Third Party Components and Libraries

Which external software components will be used? What dependencies on software libraries do exist? How do you document this?

Code

Which programming language(s) do you plan to use?
The software languages go hand in hand with different methods, focuses and required skill levels. Here you can document which language(s) you choose and why. Examples of software languages can be Java, Python, R, etc.

At this point it is also useful to document whether technical standards are relevant for the development of software. Examples include [IEC Standard 62304](#) for software in medical applications, or [ECSS-E-ST-40C](#) for software in space applications, or [DICOM](#) for the exchange of medical image data.

Which technology or process is used for versioning?
Versioning code during development is strongly recommended. Applications such as Git systems are widespread.

Personal API Token

[Feedback](#)

[Language](#) ▾

[Jürgen Windeck](#) ▾

API token

Your API token is: [REDACTED]

[Regenerate token](#)

You can use this token in HTTP requests by using the `Authorization` Header:

Authorization: Token [REDACTED]

Preview: RO-crate export plugin

example.com Management Admin Sprache Anna Admin

RDMO Test

Beschreibung Keine Beschreibung vorhanden.

Katalog RDMO

Ansichten

Ansichten werden anhand der im Projekt gegebenen Antworten erstellt und können anschließend in verschiedenen Formaten exportiert werden. Zu Beginn sind alle Ansichten leer. Bitte beantworten Sie einige Fragen, indem Sie **Fragen beantworten** (oben in der Seitenleiste) besuchen.

Ansehen	Beschreibung
Projekt Test Ansicht C	Lorem Ipsum dolor sit amet, consetetur sadipscing elitr, sed diam nonumy eirmod tempor invidunt ut labore et dolore magna aliquyam erat, sed diam voluptua.

Mitgliedschaften

Hier können Sie sehen, wer auf das Projekt zugreifen kann und weitere Mitglieder einladen. Über die Benutzerrollen können Sie verwalten, welche Rechte die Nutzenden haben. Sofern Sie nicht der letzte Besitzer sind, können Sie das Projekt mit der Schaltfläche neben Ihrem Namen verlassen.

- Optionen
- Fragen beantworten
- Antworten anzeigen
- Projektinformationen bearbeiten
- Projektkatalog bearbeiten
- Übergeordnetes Projekt bearbeiten
- Projekt Ansichten bearbeiten
- Projekt entfernen
- Mitglied hinzufügen
- Snapshot erstellen
- Zurück zu den Projekten

Export

- as RDMO XML
- as CSV (comma separated)
- as CSV (semicolon separated)
- as ro-crate zip**


```
JSON Rohdaten Kopfzeilen
Speichern Kopieren Alle einklappen Alle ausklappen JSON durchsuchen
@context: "https://rdm.org/ro/crate/1.1/context"
graph TD
  0["Dataset"]
  0["datePublished: 2023-08-11T12:48:47+00:00"]
  0["description: Abstract, das mache ich in meiner Forschung"]
  0["hasPart: 0: Simulationsdaten, 1: Video"]
  0["keywords: Keyword1, keyword 2, keyword 3"]
  0["name: RDMO Test"]
  1["ro-crate-metadata.json"]
  1["@type: CreativeWork"]
  1["about: 1: Video"]
  1["conformsTo: https://rdm.org/ro/crate/1.1"]
  2["Simulationsdaten"]
  2["@type: Dataset"]
  2["author: W3a2eCh-a1d3-4899-91f1-c4ac5646933"]
  2["@id: W3a2eCh-a1d3-4899-91f1-c4ac5646933"]
  2["description: Viele schöne Daten"]
  2["keywords: "]
  2["name: Simulationsdaten"]
  3["Video"]
```


example.com Management Admin

Export RO-Crate

Select dataset of your project

- Simulationsdaten
- Video

Export RO-Crate Abbrechen

Preview: DMP Review Service

The screenshot shows the NFDI4ing interface for the 'DMP Review Service Test'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Management' and 'Admin' menus, and a user profile for 'Jürgen Windeck'. The main content area is titled 'DMP Review Service Test' and includes a 'Description' section with the text 'No description available.' and a 'Catalog' section with the text 'NFDI4ing DMP_Review_Service' and 'Testkatalog für den DMP Review Service.'. Below this is a 'Tasks' section with a table of tasks. The table has columns for 'Task', 'Description', 'Start Date', 'Status', and 'Priority'. The tasks listed are 'DMP Review Service Test', 'DMP Review Service Test', 'DMP Review Service Test', and 'DMP Review Service Test'. On the right side, there is a sidebar with 'Options' and 'Answer questions' sections, including links for 'View answers', 'Update project information', and 'Update project catalog'.

Management Admin Feedback Language Jürgen Windeck

DMP Review Service Test

Description No description available.

Catalog NFDI4ing DMP_Review_Service
Testkatalog für den DMP Review Service.

Tasks

Task	Description	Start Date	Status	Priority
DMP Review Service Test	No description available.		Open	High
DMP Review Service Test	No description available.		Open	High
DMP Review Service Test	No description available.		Open	High
DMP Review Service Test	No description available.		Open	High

Options

Answer questions

View answers

Update project information
Update project catalog

Catalog Version 2 - We need your help!

Get to know Alex, Betty, Caden, Doris, Ellen, Frank, Golo

NFDI4ing Base service S1

Quality assurance in RDM processes and metrics for FAIR data

Thank you

Contact / Feedback

rdmo@nfdi4ing.de

NFDI4ing

Feedback Language ▾ Jürgen Windeck ▾

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- simulation data
- measurement data e.g. from test benches
- experimental, microbial and/or genomic data

Overview

Project: [NFDI4ing Vorlage Test](#)
Catalog: [NFDI4ing_template](#)
[Back to my projects](#)

Progress